

MAIN APPROACHES OF FORMATIVE ASSESMENT IN TEACHING LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In recent years rapidly evolving educational landscape, but assessment of educational system has some conflicts. This article explores formative assessment which is ongoing and used to monitor student learning during instruction. There are various methods and approaches to conducting formative assessment.*

Keywords: *assessment, formative, method, quiz, test, project, observation, discussions, feedback, rubrics, checklist, self-assessment, peer assessment.*

Formative assessment is an ongoing process that involves gathering information about students' learning progress to provide feedback and guide instructional decisions. There are various methods and approaches to conducting formative assessment, including:

1. Observations: Teachers can observe students in class, during group work, or individual tasks to assess their understanding, skills, and behaviors.
2. Questioning: Asking students questions during lessons, discussions, or activities can help assess their understanding, critical thinking skills, and problem-solving abilities.
3. Quizzes and Tests: Short quizzes or informal tests can be used to assess students' knowledge and understanding of a topic or concept.
4. Peer Assessment: Students can provide feedback to their peers on their work, projects, or presentations, which can help them reflect on their own work and improve.
5. Self-Assessment: Students can reflect on their own learning progress, set goals, and evaluate their own performance to identify areas for improvement.
6. Checklists and Rubrics: Using checklists or rubrics to assess students' work based on specific criteria and learning objectives can provide clear feedback on their performance.
7. Exit Tickets: Quick assessments at the end of a lesson or class can help gauge students' understanding of key concepts and identify any misconceptions.
8. Formative Feedback: Providing timely and specific feedback to students on their work, assignments, or assessments can help them understand their strengths and areas for improvement.
9. Peer Review: Having students review and provide feedback on each other's work can promote collaboration, communication skills, and critical thinking.
10. Interactive Technology Tools: Using technology tools such as online quizzes, interactive whiteboards, polling apps, or learning management systems can enhance formative assessment practices.

By using a combination of these methods and approaches, teachers can effectively monitor students' progress, provide targeted support, and promote continuous improvement in learning outcomes.

Observation is a method of formative assessment that involves watching and closely monitoring students' behaviors, interactions, and performance in various learning contexts.

Observations can provide valuable insights into students' understanding, skills, attitudes, and engagement levels. Teachers can use observations to gather information about individual students or groups of students, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and make informed instructional decisions.

During observations, teachers may take notes, record data, or use checklists to document specific behaviors or actions exhibited by students. Observations can be conducted in various settings, such as classroom activities, group work, discussions, presentations, or hands-on tasks. By observing students in action, teachers can assess their comprehension of concepts, problem-solving abilities, social skills, collaboration with peers, and overall engagement in the learning process.

Observations can be informal and ongoing, integrated seamlessly into daily teaching practices, or they can be more structured and focused on specific learning objectives or behaviors. The information gathered through observations can help teachers adjust their teaching strategies, provide targeted feedback to students, differentiate instruction based on individual needs, and create a supportive learning environment that promotes student growth and success.

Questioning is a formative assessment strategy that involves asking students open-ended or closed-ended questions to assess their understanding, knowledge, reasoning skills, and critical thinking abilities. Questioning is an essential tool for teachers to gauge students' comprehension, provoke deeper thinking, encourage active participation, and promote meaningful discussions in the classroom.

There are different types of questions that teachers can use during instruction, such as:

1. Open-ended questions: These questions require students to provide detailed responses, explanations, or opinions. Open-ended questions encourage critical thinking, creativity, and higher-order thinking skills.

2. Closed-ended questions: These questions have specific answers that can be answered with a single word or a short phrase. Closed-ended questions are useful for checking factual knowledge, comprehension, and recall.

3. Probing questions: These questions are follow-up questions that prompt students to elaborate on their initial responses, clarify their thinking, or provide additional details. Probing questions help teachers delve deeper into students' understanding and reasoning.

4. Socratic questioning: This type of questioning is used to stimulate critical thinking and challenge students' assumptions by encouraging them to analyze, evaluate, and reflect on their ideas. Socratic questioning promotes intellectual inquiry and helps students develop logical reasoning skills.

By using questioning as a formative assessment strategy, teachers can assess students' understanding in real-time, identify misconceptions or gaps in knowledge, guide discussions, facilitate peer interactions, and provide timely feedback to support student learning. Questioning also encourages active engagement, promotes student participation, and fosters a collaborative learning environment where students can construct meaning and deepen their understanding of the content.

Quizzes and tests are formal assessment tools used by teachers to evaluate students' knowledge, understanding, skills, and abilities in a specific subject or topic. Both quizzes and tests are designed to measure students' learning outcomes, assess their progress, and provide feedback on their academic performance. However, there are some key differences between quizzes and tests:

1. Quizzes:

- Quizzes are shorter assessments that typically cover a specific topic, concept, or lesson.
- Quizzes are often used as formative assessments to check for understanding, reinforce learning, and identify areas where students may need additional support.

- Quizzes may consist of multiple-choice questions, true/false statements, short-answer questions, or matching exercises.

- Quizzes are usually low-stakes assessments that contribute to students' overall grades but have a smaller impact compared to tests.

- Quizzes can be administered frequently throughout a unit or course to monitor student progress and provide ongoing feedback.

2. Tests:

- Tests are longer assessments that cover a broader range of topics or concepts from a unit, chapter, or entire course.

- Tests are typically used as summative assessments to evaluate students' mastery of the content and determine their final grades.

- Tests may include a variety of question types, such as multiple-choice, short-answer, essay questions, problem-solving tasks, or performance-based assessments.

- Tests are higher-stakes assessments that carry more weight in students' overall grades and may be used to measure their readiness for advancement or achievement of learning objectives.

- Tests are usually administered at the end of a unit, semester, or academic year to assess students' cumulative knowledge and understanding.

Overall, both quizzes and tests play important roles in the assessment process and provide valuable information about students' learning progress and achievement. Quizzes help teachers gauge student understanding on a smaller scale and provide timely feedback, while tests offer a comprehensive evaluation of students' knowledge and skills over a longer period.

Peer assessment is a form of evaluation in which students provide feedback and evaluate the work of their peers. In peer assessment, students assess each other's performance, projects, assignments, or contributions based on specific criteria or guidelines set by the teacher or instructor. Peer assessment can be used in various educational settings, including classrooms, group projects, presentations, and online courses.

Key features of peer assessment include:

1. Feedback: Students provide constructive feedback to their peers on their work, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. This feedback can help students learn from each other, gain different perspectives, and enhance their understanding of the subject matter.

2. Criteria: Peer assessment is typically based on predetermined criteria or rubrics that outline the expectations for the assignment or task. These criteria help guide students in evaluating their peers' work objectively and consistently.

3. Collaboration: Peer assessment promotes collaboration and communication among students, as they engage in discussions, share ideas, and support each other in the learning process. It encourages active participation and engagement in the evaluation process.

4. Reflection: Through peer assessment, students have the opportunity to reflect on their own work as well as the work of their peers. This reflection can deepen their understanding of the subject matter, improve their critical thinking skills, and enhance their self-assessment abilities.

5. Accountability: Peer assessment encourages students to take responsibility for their learning and performance. By evaluating their peers' work and receiving feedback from others, students become more accountable for their efforts and outcomes.

6. Diversity of perspectives: Peer assessment allows students to receive feedback from a diverse range of perspectives and experiences, which can enrich their learning experience and help them see different approaches to solving problems or completing tasks.

Overall, peer assessment is a valuable tool that promotes student engagement, collaboration, critical thinking, and self-reflection. It can enhance the learning process by providing students with opportunities to actively participate in the evaluation of their own and their peers' work, ultimately contributing to their academic growth and development.

Checklists and rubrics are two common tools used in education to assess and evaluate student performance, provide feedback, and guide learning. While both tools serve similar purposes, they have distinct characteristics and applications.

1. Checklist:

- A checklist is a simple, itemized list of criteria or tasks that need to be completed or checked off.

- Checklists are typically used to track completion of specific steps, tasks, or requirements in a systematic manner.

- Checklists are often binary in nature, indicating whether a task has been completed or not.

- Checklists are useful for tracking progress, ensuring all necessary components are included, and providing a clear overview of what needs to be accomplished.

- Checklists can be helpful for self-assessment, peer assessment, and teacher assessment of student work.

2. Rubrics:

- A rubric is a scoring guide that outlines criteria for assessing student performance or products across multiple dimensions.

- Rubrics provide detailed descriptions of performance expectations at different levels of proficiency, often using a scale or levels (e.g., exemplary, proficient, developing, emerging).

- Rubrics help clarify expectations, provide consistent and objective feedback, and guide students in understanding how their work will be evaluated.

- Rubrics can be holistic (evaluating overall performance) or analytic (evaluating specific criteria separately).

- Rubrics are commonly used for grading assignments, projects, presentations, essays, and other types of student work.

In summary, while checklists focus on completion of tasks and provide a simple way to track progress, rubrics offer a more detailed and structured framework for assessing performance against specific criteria. Both tools can be valuable in educational settings to support student learning, provide feedback, and promote clarity in assessment practices. Teachers may choose to use checklists for straightforward tasks or procedural steps and rubrics for more complex assignments that require detailed evaluation across multiple dimensions.

Exit tickets are a formative assessment tool used by teachers to gauge student understanding, gather feedback, and assess learning at the end of a lesson or class period. Exit tickets are typically brief, targeted questions or prompts that students respond to before leaving the classroom or transitioning to the next activity. The purpose of exit tickets is to provide teachers with immediate feedback on student comprehension, identify areas of confusion or misconceptions, and inform future instructional decisions.

Key features of exit tickets include:

1. Brief and focused: Exit tickets are designed to be quick and concise, usually consisting of one to three questions or prompts related to the day's lesson objectives.

2. Assessment of understanding: Exit tickets are used to assess students' comprehension of key concepts, skills, or content covered in the lesson.

3. Feedback for teachers: By reviewing students' responses to exit tickets, teachers can quickly identify areas where students may need additional support, clarification, or reteaching.

4. Informing instruction: The feedback gathered from exit tickets can help teachers adjust their teaching strategies, pacing, or content delivery to better meet the needs of their students.

5. Engagement and reflection: Exit tickets can also prompt students to reflect on their learning, articulate their understanding, and engage in metacognitive processes.

Examples of exit ticket prompts include:

- "What was the most important concept you learned today?"

- "What questions do you still have about today's lesson?"

- "How confident do you feel about applying this concept in a real-world situation?"

Overall, exit tickets serve as a valuable formative assessment tool that supports ongoing student learning, guides instructional decisions, and promotes reflection on learning outcomes.

Formative feedback is a type of feedback provided to students during the learning process to help them improve their understanding, performance, and skills. Unlike summative feedback, which is typically given at the end of an assessment or task to evaluate the final outcome, formative feedback is ongoing, timely, and focused on guiding students towards achieving their learning goals.

Key characteristics of formative feedback include:

1. Timely: Formative feedback is provided in a timely manner, allowing students to make immediate adjustments to their learning strategies or performance.

2. Specific and actionable: Formative feedback is specific and provides actionable guidance on how students can improve their work, understanding, or skills.

3. Focused on improvement: The primary goal of formative feedback is to support student growth and improvement by identifying areas of strength and areas for development.

4. Targeted: Formative feedback is tailored to individual students' needs, addressing their unique strengths, challenges, and learning goals.

5. Encouraging and supportive: Formative feedback is delivered in a supportive and constructive manner, emphasizing students' progress and potential for growth.

Examples of formative feedback include:

- Providing specific comments on a student's draft essay to help them strengthen their argument or structure.

- Offering suggestions for improvement on a math problem to guide a student towards the correct solution.

- Engaging in one-on-one conferences with students to discuss their progress, address misconceptions, and set goals for future learning.

Overall, formative feedback plays a crucial role in supporting student learning, fostering a growth mindset, and empowering students to take ownership of their learning journey. By providing ongoing guidance and support, teachers can help students develop their skills, deepen their understanding, and achieve academic success.

Peer review is a process used in academic publishing and research to ensure the quality and credibility of scholarly work. It involves experts in the field, known as peers, evaluating the research, writing, and methodology of a submitted manuscript before it is accepted for publication in a scientific journal or presented at a conference. The peer reviewers provide feedback and recommendations to the authors and the editor of the journal to help improve the quality of the work and ensure that it meets the standards of the field. Peer review helps to maintain the integrity

and reliability of scientific research by identifying errors, biases, and weaknesses in a study before it is disseminated to the broader scientific community.

Interactive technology tools are digital devices, software applications, or platforms that enable users to actively engage with content, manipulate data, and interact with the technology in real-time. These tools are designed to enhance learning, collaboration, communication, and productivity by providing interactive and engaging experiences for users. Examples of interactive technology tools include:

1. Interactive whiteboards: These are large touch-sensitive displays that allow users to interact with digital content using their fingers or a stylus. They are commonly used in classrooms and meeting rooms for presentations, brainstorming, and collaboration.

2. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) applications: These technologies create immersive digital environments that users can explore and interact with using specialized headsets or mobile devices. VR and AR applications are used in education, training, gaming, and simulation.

3. Interactive polling and survey tools: These tools allow presenters to gather real-time feedback from audiences through live polls, quizzes, and surveys. They are often used in classrooms, conferences, and corporate meetings to engage participants and assess learning outcomes.

4. Collaborative online platforms: Platforms such as Google Docs, Microsoft Teams, and Slack enable users to collaborate on documents, projects, and tasks in real-time. These tools facilitate communication, file sharing, and teamwork among individuals or groups.

5. Gamification apps: Gamification involves incorporating game elements, such as points, badges, and leaderboards, into non-game contexts to motivate and engage users. Gamification apps are used in education, fitness, productivity, and marketing to encourage participation and drive behavior change.

Overall, interactive technology tools play a crucial role in modern education, business, entertainment, and communication by providing dynamic and engaging experiences that enhance learning, collaboration, and creativity.

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